

Supplementary Table 5. Data charting for all studies assessing the association between age and GWG.

Author	Year	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Study population	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Age categories	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability factor?	Findings
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG increased with young maternal age (<20 vs 30+ yrs); odd of insufficient GWG decreased if age 20-24 or 25-29 (vs 30+ yrs old)	NS effect of young maternal age (<20 yrs as compared to 30 yrs or older) on insufficient GWG	<20 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs ≥30 yrs	No	S & NS
Ancrì, G.	1977	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study with women age 12-32 years; all women were White (with the exception of one Black woman)	98	Significantly higher GWG in adolescents (18-19 yrs) than in adults (20-24 years, 25-32 years); significantly lower GWG in oldest age group		12-17 yrs 18-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-32 years	No	S
Ba'aqeel, H. S.	1989	Saudi Ara	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents and adults who gave birth at a university hospital between January 1983 and December 1984, the majority of whom were Saudi	184		NS difference in GWG between adolescents (age ≤18 yrs) and adults (age 20-29 yrs); note: more than half of the adolescents were 18 yrs of age, and a similar proportion of adults were 20-22 yrs of age	≤18 yrs 20-29 yrs	No	NS
Beaudrot, M. E.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of primiparous adolescents and adults who gave birth in Ohio from 2006-12	251 398	Adequacy of GWG (lost weight, insufficient GWG, adequate GWG, or excessive GWG) differed significantly between age groups (<15 yrs, 15-17 yrs, 18-19 yrs, and 20-34 yrs); no post hoc tests for GWG adequacy and age		<15 yrs 15-17 yrs 18-19 yrs 20-34 yrs	No	S*
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337	Young adolescents (<15 years old) were more likely to have insufficient GWG		<15 yrs 15-17 yrs	Yes	S*
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Young women (20-34, as compared to 35+ years old) had higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG); physical violence by an intimate partner around the time of pregnancy (before and/or during) was positively and significantly associated with insufficient and excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) only among women ≥35 years	Physical abuse before and/or during pregnancy not associated with excessive or insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) in younger women (age 20 - 34 years)	20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S* & NS*

Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Low maternal age (≤24 years vs. 25-29 years) had higher odds of excessive GWG; higher maternal age (35-44 years) had lower odds of excessive GWG; higher odds of insufficient GWG in 20-34 year old & women >45 years	NS effect of age 30-34 on odds of excessive GWG; NS effects of age <20 or 35-44 years on insufficient GWG	<20 yrs 20-24.9 yrs 25-29.9 yrs 30-34.9 35-39.9 ≥40 yrs	No	S & NS
Caulfield, L. E.	1996	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and White women who delivered at John Hopkins Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics from 1987-89	3 870	Significant difference in mean age between GWG adequacy categories (but not specific to adolescents vs adults)		Continuous variable	No	S*
Chagarlamudi, H.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women attending an outpatient obstetrics/gynecology clinic that mainly serves a low-income community (2012-13) in North Carolina	410		NS effect on odds of having excessive or insufficient GWG (as compared to adequate GWG) by age	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*
Chandra, P. C.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents and adults who gave birth at a public urban hospital from January 1996 to October 1999	2 352	Young adolescents had significantly lower GWG than older adolescents and adults		13-15 yrs 16-19 yrs ≥20 yrs	No	S
Chang, T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women aged 15-24 years living in large US cities from 1998-2000; national weights were used to make data representative of births in all large US cities (populations of >200,000); all women were part of the "Fragile Families and Child Wellbeing Study"	1,034 (unweighted)		NS association between age (range of 15-24 years) and excessive or insufficient GWG	15-16 yrs 17-18 yrs 19-21 yrs 22-24 yrs	No	NS*
Chasan-Taber, L.	2008	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770	Higher risk of excessive GWG in women 30-39 years old (as compared to 20-24 years old)	NS effect of age on insufficient GWG; NS effect of younger age <20 or 25-29 yrs vs 20-24) on odds of excessive GWG	<20 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-39 yrs	Yes	S* & NS
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to age (age range: 16-40 years old)	16-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-30 yrs >30 yrs	Yes	NS*

Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293		Age (age range: 16-40 years old) not associated with adequacy of GWG	<19 yrs 19-23 yrs 24-29 yrs ≥30 yrs	Yes	NS*
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Among Asian women: higher risk of insufficient GWG in older women (18-34 years vs 35+ yrs)	NS difference in risk of excessive GWG according to age	18-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S* & NS*
Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on maternal age (<20, 20-29, 30+ yrs)		<20 yrs 20-29 yrs ≥30 yrs	Yes	S*
Cunningham, S.D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women age 14-21 yrs old enrolled in the CenteringPregnancy Plus RCT (a multi-site prenatal care intervention) from 2008-2012; hospitals chosen for the RCT primarily served women who have low income and women from minority groups	505		Women having adequate vs excessive GWG did not differ by mean age (age range: 14-21 yrs old, with mean of 18.62 yrs)	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Overweight</u> : higher odds of excessive GWG if age under 19 (vs 25-29 yrs)	Age: NS effect of adolescent age on excessive or insufficient GWG for all BMI groups (except overweight - higher risk of excessive GWG)	<19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S & NS
Elchert, J.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of women who gave birth in Ohio from 2006-12	326 368	Increased risk of insufficient GWG in adolescents (vs adults age 20-34 yrs); lower risk of excessive GWG in 15-17 year olds vs adults	NS difference in excessive GWG risk between adolescents <15 and 18-19 yrs old and adults (age 20-34)	<15 yrs 15-17 yrs 18-19 yrs 20-34 yrs	No	S & NS
Fernandez, I. D.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Population registry of adolescents who gave birth in Upstate New York from 1996-2002	6 995		Mean GWG did not vary significantly by age (<16 vs 16-20 yrs)	<16 yrs 16-20 yrs	Yes	NS

Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959		NS effect of age (mean age 30 yrs) on odds of excessive GWG	Continuous variable	No	NS*
Galvez-Myles, R.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents (13-19 years) and adults (25-34 years) who delivered at 2 hospitals in Texas from January 1999 to April 2001 and were enrolled in the state's Medicaid program	685	Adolescents (≤ 19 yrs) had significantly higher total GWG than adults (remained significant after controlling for county type [rural or urban])	NS difference when total GWG of adolescents ≤ 17 yrs was compared to adult controls	≤ 17 yrs ≤ 19 yrs Adults (mean age: 28.4 yrs)	Yes	S & NS
Groth, S.	2008	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Black, primiparous adolescents (12-19 yrs of age at the beginning of pregnancy) with a low income and at least two of three sociodemographic risk conditions: unmarried, <12 yrs of education, or unemployed	330		NS difference in total GWG based on age (<16 yrs, 16-17 yrs, 18-19 yrs)	<16 yrs 16-17 yrs 18-19 yrs	Yes	NS*
Guilloty, N.	2015	USA (Puerto Rico)	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in northern Puerto Rico from 2011-14	160		NS associations were observed between GWG adequacy and age (18-29 years vs 30-40 years)	18-29 yrs 30-40 yrs	Yes	NS*
Haeri, S.	2010	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	All births to adolescents at a single site from 2000-04	456		NS difference in adequate vs excessive GWG by age (≤ 15 yrs vs 16-18 yrs)	≤ 15 yrs 16-18 yrs	Yes	NS
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053	Significant differences in GWG adequacy by age (18-24 yrs, 25-34 yrs, ≥ 35 yrs)		18-24 yrs 25-34 yrs ≥ 35 yrs	No	S*
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported ; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300		NS difference in GWG adequacy according to age (<20 , 20-24, 25-29, 30-34, 35-39, 40+; no limit to age of women in study, but population was mainly adults)	<20 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs 35-39 yrs ≥ 40 yrs	No	NS*
Hediger, M. L.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Primigravida adolescents (<16 years) and adults (18-29 years) who gave birth from 1985-95 and were enrolled in the Camden Study	605	Compared to adults, adolescents had significantly higher GWG rate		<16 yrs 18-29 yrs (most were 18-19 yrs)	No	S

Hediger, M. L.	1994	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Women from Camden who were <16 yrs old (primiparous or multiparous) or were 18-29 yrs old (primiparous); women who reported breastfeeding following the birth of their child were excluded, as this can impact weight loss	608		NS difference in GWG at 28 weeks gestation, from 28 weeks gestation to delivery, or in total GWG between adolescents age 13-15 yrs, 16-18 yrs, or adults age 19-29 yrs	13-15 yrs 16-18 yrs 19-29 yrs	No	NS
Hediger, M. L.	1990	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 419	Young age (≤ 14 years vs 17-18 yrs) was associated with higher weight gain from 20 wks gestation onward	NS difference in GWG between adolescents 15-16 yrs vs 17-18 yrs old	≤ 14 yrs 15-16 yrs 17-18 yrs	Yes	S & NS
Herring, S. J.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Urban, low-income, primarily Black women seeking prenatal care at a university hospital from 2009-11	94		NS association between excessive GWG and age (<25 vs ≥ 25)	<25 yrs ≥ 25 yrs	Yes	NS*
Hickey, C. A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150		NS association between low GWG and age	17-19 yrs 20-25 yrs 26-30 yrs 31-35 yrs	Yes	NS*
Hickey, C. A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income, multiparous Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806		NS association between insufficient GWG and age	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*
Hoff, C.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Measured; no GWG guidelines identified	Nulliparous, primarily Black, low-income adolescents (< 17 years) and adults (17-31 years) who gave birth at a specific hospital in South Alabama from 1974-79	1 844	Adults: higher GWG in White women than Black women	NS difference in GWG between adults and adolescents of same race; in adolescents: NS difference in GWG between Black and White	12-16 yrs 17-31 yrs ('adults')	Yes	NS
Houde, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in the USA in 2012	3 960 796	GWG varied significantly between adults and adolescents		12-19 yrs >20 yrs	No	S

Howie, L. D.	2003	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Women included in the 2000 US Natality File (excluding women from California, as GWG there is not collected)	2 796 805	Odds of excessive GWG (>40 lbs) higher in adolescents and young adults (vs age 25-29); odds of excessive GWG lower in older adults	≤15 yrs 16-17 yrs 18-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs 35-39 yrs ≥40 yrs	No	S
Incollingo Rodriguez, A. C.	2019	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the multi-site Community Child Health Network study who indicated that they experience everyday discrimination due to their weight or height	214	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG or total GWG according to age (age range: 18-40 years)	Continuous variable	No	NS*
Inoue, S.	2013	Japan	Cross-sectional	Measured; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at a specific hospital in Shizuoka Prefecture from 1997-2010	15 020	<u>Among underweight women:</u> lower odds of excessive GWG if age 25+ (as compared to <25 years) <u>Among normal weight women:</u> age >35 years was associated with higher odds of insufficient GWG, older age (25+) decreased odds of excessive GWG <u>Among overweight women:</u> age >35 decreased risk of insufficient GWG	<u>Underweight women:</u> NS effect of age on risk of insufficient GWG <25 yrs 25-35 yrs ≥35 yrs <u>Normal weight women:</u> NS effect of age 25-35 (vs <25) on insufficient GWG <u>Overweight women:</u> NS effect of age 25-35 on insufficient GWG or age 25+ on excessive GWG	No	S* & NS*
Ishitsuka, K.	2019	Japan	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Adolescent (<20 years old) and adult (20-34 years old) women involved in the Japan Environment and Children's Study, a multi-site, nationwide cohort with deliveries from 2011-14	74 706	Differences in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between adolescents (<20 yrs) and adults	14-19 yrs 20-34 yrs	No	S

Johnson, P. J.	2002	USA	Retrospective IOM 1990	Medical record; Primarily low-income, urban women seeking prenatal care at a specific clinic from 1997-98	578	<p><u>In adults</u>: higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if any report of abuse (vs. no abuse; type and timing of abuse not considered), history of physical abuse only, history of physical abuse with or without history of physical abuse; higher odds of excessive GWG if history of sexual abuse with or without history of physical abuse, any abuse</p> <p><u>When all subjects grouped together</u>: higher odds of insufficient GWG if history of physical abuse only</p> <p>-</p> <p><u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories (insufficient, adequate, excessive)</u>: significant difference by education (looked at inadequate education, i.e. not having completed the expected number of years of schooling; only significant for adolescents), parity (1st birth vs 1+ previous birth; only significant for adults)</p>	<p><u>In adolescents</u>: NS association between insufficient and excessive GWG and any type or timing of abuse; <u>in adults</u>: NS effect on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG if a woman experienced physical or sexual abuse during pregnancy; NS effect on odds of excessive GWG if a woman had a history of physical abuse only</p> <p>-</p> <p><u>When all ages grouped together</u>: NS effect of current physical/sexual abuse, history of sexual abuse with or without physical abuse, or any abuse on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG; NS effect of history of physical abuse only on odds of excessive GWG</p> <p>-</p> <p><u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories</u>: NS association with age (looked at distribution within adolescents and adults, but did not compare adolescents to adults), alcohol use, or illicit drug use; for adults only: NS association with</p>	Continuous variable (when looking at distribution of women in GWG categories) <20 yrs ≥20 yrs	Yes	S* & NS*
Johnston, C. S.	1992	USA	Retrospective IOM 1990	Medical record; Middle-class to upper-class women who gave birth under the care of the private CIGNA Healthplan of Arizona	329		NS difference in total GWG between adolescents (14-17 yrs old) and adults (18-25 yrs old)	14-17 yrs old 18-25 yrs old	No	NS
Johnston, C. S.	1991	USA	Retrospective no GWG guideline identified	Medical record; A subset of women who gave birth from 1987 to 1989 and had the private CIGNA Healthplan of Arizona	423		NS difference in total GWG, GWG after 3 months of pregnancy or GWG after 6 months of pregnancy between adolescents (14-17 yrs old) and young adults (18-25 yrs old)	14-17 yrs old 18-25 yrs old	No	NS
Joseph, N. P.	2008	USA	Retrospective IOM 1990	Medical record; Adolescent caregivers (age 21 or less at time of enrollment with a child 18 months or younger) recruited from a single clinic from 2002-2005	102		NS difference in change in GWG by age	Age measured as a continuous variable	Yes	NS*

Jung, Y.M.	2017	Korea	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth to term infants and resided in a single city in South Korea	75		NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) by mean maternal age; NS difference in total GWG by household income (<3,000,000 won vs ≥3,000,000 won)	Mean age	No	NS*
Ketterlinus, R. D.	1990	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; National Center for Health Statistics 1980	Black or White, primiparous women enrolled in the National Longitudinal Survey of Work Experience of Youth; all women were between 13 and 30 years old	1 994	Significant difference in total GWG by age group		<15 yrs 16-18 yrs 19-21 yrs ≥22 yrs	No	S
Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to age		Continuous variable	No	S*
Kinnunen, T. I.	2016	Norway	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care in Eastern Oslo from 2008-10	632	Negative relationship between GWG and age (age range not identified, but population consisted primarily of adults)		Continuous variable	No	S*
Kirchengast, S.	2003	Austria	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study with primiparous women age 12-29 yrs who attended all prenatal check-ups and gave birth from 1985-1995 at a university clinic; adolescents age 12-16 had to have received psychosocial support	8 011		NS difference in total GWG between individuals <17 yrs, 17-19 yrs, or 20-29 yrs of age	<17 yrs old 17-19 yrs old 20-29 yrs old	No	NS
Koh, H.	2013	Singapore	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG guideline by Wong et al., 2000	All women who delivered at a specific hospital from Jan-Apr 2008 (approximately 30% of infants in Singapore are delivered at this hospital every year)	1 166	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate): age ≤19 yrs (as compared to 20-30 yrs); lower odds of excessive GWG if older (≥31 yrs as compared to 20-30 yrs)	NS effect of adolescent age (as compared to 20-30 yrs old) on odds of excessive GWG	≤19 yrs 20-30 yrs ≥31 years	No	S & NS

Koleilat, M.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Primarily Hispanic women, all with a low-income and enrolled in the Public Health Foundation Enterprises WIC Program in Southern California	23 840	Lower odds of excessive GWG if higher age (no limit to population age)	Continuous variable	Yes	S*
Kominiarek, M. A.	2018b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Large multi-site study with random selection of women who gave birth at one of the sites from 2008-11	29 861	Significant differences in GWG adequacy (inadequate, adequate, excessive) according to age (mean age approx. 29 yrs)	Continuous variable	No	S*
Korencan, S.	2017	Slovenia	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	All primiparous Slovenian women aged up to 24 years who gave birth from 2008-12	13 663	Significant difference in GWG adequacy between adolescents (≤ 17 yrs and ≤ 19 yrs) and adults (20-24 yrs)	≤ 17 yrs ≤ 19 yrs 20-24 yrs	No	S
Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥ 15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	NS difference in odds of GWG adequacy (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) according to age (<20, 30-39, 40+ yrs vs 20-29)	<20 yrs 20-29 yrs 30-39 yrs ≥ 40 yrs	No	NS
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	NS difference in women with adequate vs excessive GWG according to age (age range not identified, but primarily adults [average age: 25.5 years])	Continuous variable	No	NS*
Kuo, C. P.	2010	Taiwan	Retrospective	Self-reported; Taiwan Bureau of Health Promotion	Adolescents (<20 years old) and adults (20-35 years old) included in Taiwan's Birth Registration Database of 2005	9 880	Significantly more common for adolescents to have insufficient GWG (<12 kg) as compared to adults	<20 yrs 20-35 yrs	No	S
Kurzel, R. B.	1997	USA	Prospective	Method used for obtaining GWG unclear; no GWG guideline identified	Predominantly Hispanic, immigrant adolescents (age 13-19 years) and adults ≥ 20 years)	2 440	Higher total GWG in adolescent (vs adults 20+ yrs), and wider range of GWG	13-19 yrs ≥ 20 yrs	Yes	S
Lindberg, S.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at UW Health from 2007-12	7 385	Factors increasing odds of excessive GWG: NS effect of age 18-19, 20-24, 25-29, 35-39 yrs (vs 30-34 yrs) on odds of insufficient GWG; NS effect of age 18-19 (vs 30-34 yrs) on odds of excessive GWG	18-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs 35-39 yrs ≥ 40 yrs	No	S* & NS

Loris, P.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; Morse et al. 1975 (standard GWG curve)	Adolescents age 13-19 years in the Sacramento area who attended adolescent-specific pregnancy clinics or programs from 1979 -82	145		NS difference in total GWG based on age (13-15, 16-17, 18-19 yrs)	13-15 yrs 16-17 yrs 18-19 yrs	Yes	NS*
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM 1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG with younger age (15-19, 20-24, and 25-29 years of age as compared to 35-39)	NS difference in prevalence of insufficient GWG according to age (age range: 15-40+ years old)	15-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs 35-39 yrs ≥40 yrs	No	S & NS
Marsiglio, W.	1988	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; GWG ≤15lbs considered insufficient, ≥50lbs excessive	Women who participated in the National Longitudinal Survey of Labour Market Experience of Youth; sample weighted to be representative of a national cross-section of women age 19-27 years in 1984; women were primiparous at the time of their interview	6 015	Predictors of insufficient GWG: being ≤18 or younger or 19-20 years old at time of birth (vs ≥21 yrs); predictors of excessive GWG: age 19-20 at time of birth (vs ≥21 yrs)	NS effect of being ≤18 years old on excessive GWG	≤18 yrs 19-20 yrs ≥21 yrs	No	S & NS
Meng, Y.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black women seeking prenatal care at one of two clinics from 2008-11, all of whom were ≥18 years of age and enrolled in Medicaid and/or the Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children	55		NS association between GWG and age (age range: 18-36 years)	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*
Meserole, L. P.	1984	USA	Prospective and retrospective	Medical record and measured; Committee on Maternal Nutrition weight gain curve	Primiparous adolescents (<19 years old) participating in one of two adolescent pregnancy programs in Washington state; a standard adult curve was used for comparison	80	Adolescents had significantly greater GWG than the adult standard curve; younger adolescents had lower GWG than older adolescents		13-15 yrs 16-18 yrs Adults (represented by standard GWG curve for adults)	No	S

Ochsenbein-Kolble, N.	2007	Switzerl and	Cross-sectional	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	White, Asian, and Black women at the Obstetric Outpatient Department at Zurich University Hospital from January 1996 - February 2000	4 034		NS effect of age on GWG in White women (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)	Continuous variable	No	NS*
Park, J. H.	2011	Korea	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified (no official guidelines in Korea)	Single-site study of women who gave birth at a university hospital from 2005-07	2 311		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to age (age range not indicated, but mean age of 31.7)	Continuous variable	No	NS*
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Decreased odds of insufficient GWG if older (25-34 vs 18-24 yrs); decreased odds of excessive GWG if older (25-34 or 35+ yrs vs 18-24 yrs)	NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG if age 35+ (vs 18-24 yrs); NS effect on insufficient or excessive GWG if adolescent (<18 years as compared to 18-24)	<18 yrs 18-24 yrs 25-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S* & NS
Perry, R. L.	1996	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents (<16 years old), and adults (18-29 years old) who participated in the Camden Study	387	Significantly higher GWG in young adolescents (mean age: 14.7, SD 0.7 yrs); insufficient GWG significantly more common in adults/older adolescents (mean age: 19.8, SD 2.2 yrs) vs young adolescents		<16 yrs 18-29 yrs	No	S
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on age (<20, 20-29, 30-34, 35-39, 40-44, 45+)		<20 yrs 20-29 yrs 30-34 yrs 35-39yrs 40-44 yrs ≥45 yrs	No	S*
Power, M. L.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with primarily White non-Hispanic women in rural counties in Pennsylvania who gave birth from 2006-15	18 217		NS association between maternal age and total GWG (mean age: 26.9 yrs)	Not identified	Yes	NS*
Ratan, B. M.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Low-income women with obesity who enrolled in prenatal care at a specific clinic in Houston, Texas from September 2013 August 2017; all women were receiving social assistance (CHIP Perinate or Medicaid)	772		NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, excessive) according to age (only exception: age 31-35 had higher odds of excessive GWG but became NS in multivariate analysis)	15-20 yrs 21-25 yrs 26-30 yrs 31-35 yrs ≥35 yrs	Yes	NS*

Restall, A.	2014	New Zealand, Australia, Ireland	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site cohort study with nulliparous women from 2004-11	1 950	Higher odds of excessive GWG if age 24 or less, 25-29, 30-34 years old (as compared to 35+)	≤24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S*	
Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving Non-Latina White and Latina women	571		NS effect of age (15-19, 20-24, 30-34, and 35+ vs 25-29 yrs) on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG	15-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-29 yrs 30-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	NS*
Sangi-Haghpeykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282		NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to mean age (age range not indicated, but mean age of 28.4 years)	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*
Scholl, T. O.	1984	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women who attended a specific prenatal center in Camden and gave birth in 1980; most participants were receiving welfare and were enrolled in the Supplemental Food Program for Women, Infants, and Children; half the participants were ≤15 years old, and the other half was ≥20 years old	64	Higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in adolescents	≤15 yrs ≥20 yrs	Yes	S	
Scholl, T. O.	1995	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Women age 12-29 with a low-income and a normal BMI; most women were Puerto Rican Hispanic or Black (data from Camden Study)	274	Excessive rate of GWG (as compared to low or moderate rate of GWG) significantly more prevalent in age 15 or less (other age groups: 16-18, 19-29)	≤15 yrs 16-18 yrs 19-29 yrs	Yes	S	
Schumacher, T. L.	2018	Australia	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Indigenous women, or women carrying an Indigenous child, who sought prenatal care at one of three sites in New South Wales	110		NS relationship between GWG adequacy and age (no age range identified; mean age 25.1 years)	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*

Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with primiparous (at any age vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs); negative association with being multiparous (only when <20 or >29 yrs vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs) Multivariate logistic regression for insufficient GWG (<21 lbs for underweight/normal weight women, <10 lbs for overweight/obese women): for normal/underweight, decreased odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous (only if <20 or 20-29 yrs)	NS association between total GWG (for all women) and multiparous at <20 yrs old or >29.1 yrs old NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for all women): multiparity at any age; specific to overweight/obese women: NS effect of being primiparous (any age); in underweight/normal weight women: NS effect of being primiparous (if >29 years old)	<20 yrs 20-29 yrs >29 yrs	Yes	S & NS
Stevens-Simon, C.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Black adolescents age 13-17 years at conception	108		NS difference in rate of GWG (in kg/week) between younger and older adolescents (<16 yrs old vs 16-18 yrs old)	<16 yrs old 16-18 yrs old	Yes	NS*
Stevens-Simon, C.	1993a	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Black adolescents (<20 yrs old at conception) with a low-income who gave give from 1986-1989	141		NS difference in total GWG (adjusted to represent a 40-week gestational period) between younger and older adolescents (<16 yrs old vs 16-19 yrs old)	<16 yrs old 16-19 yrs old	Yes	NS*
Stogianni, A.	2019	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guidelines identified	Women with and without diabetes who were admitted to a specific hospital in Kronoberg from January 2009 - December 2012	280		Among women with diabetes or without diabetes, maternal age >30 yrs was not significantly associated with high GWG (GWG ≥8 kg)	<30 yrs ≥30 yrs	No	NS*
Sukanich, A. C.	1986	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Women who delivered at a single hospital in Pittsburgh from 1970-1977 without medical problems prior to pregnancy	694		NS difference in total GWG by age (<16 vs 20-24 yrs old)	<16 yrs old 20-24 yrs old	No	NS
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if younger (18-24 yrs vs 25+ yrs); increased odds of excessive GWG if younger (18-24 yrs vs 25+ yrs)		18-24 yrs ≥25 yrs	No	S*

Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988		NS effect of age (18-24, 25-34, 35+ yrs) on general adequacy of GWG (looked at distribution of women in insufficient, adequate and excessive categories)	18-24 yrs 25-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	Yes	NS*
Wang, C. S.	1999	Taiwan	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescent (<20 years old) and adult primigravidas who gave birth from June 1994 - May 1995 in Kaohsiung County	1 146	Significant difference in GWG (<12 kg vs 12+ kg) by maternal age (<18 yrs, 18-19, 20-24, 25+ yrs)		<18 yrs 18-19 yrs 20-24 yrs ≥25 yrs	No	S*
Wang, S. C.	2012	Taiwan	Retrospective	Self-reported; Taiwan Bureau of Health Promotion	Primiparous adolescents (<20 years old) and adults (35-49 years old) who gave birth in Taiwan in 2005	1 236	Odds of insufficient GWG (12 kg or less) significantly higher in adolescents (<20 years) as compared to adults (>35 years)		<20 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	S
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528		NS effect of age category (15-19, 20-24, 25-34 vs 35+ years)	15-19 yrs 20-24 yrs 25-34 yrs ≥35 yrs	No	NS
Woolfolk, C. L.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of adolescents who gave birth in the USA in 2012	211 403	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (prevalence of insufficient, adequate, excessive) according to age (≤ 15 vs 15-19 yrs)		≤ 15 yrs 15-19 yrs	Yes	S*
Wright, C.	2013	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low-income urban women enrolled in a community-based participatory research study; all women attended a social service and advocacy agency for low-income women	101		NS difference in GWG category (adequate vs excessive) by age (mean age 24.6 yrs)	Continuous variable	Yes	NS*

* Study did not specifically indicate differences in GWG between adolescents and adults